

TABLE 1 - MIXED LIGAND COMPLEX FORMATION CONSTANTS OF SOME HETEROCHELATES OF Ni(II) AT 30°

L	log K Ni.IMDA Ni.IMDA.L	L	log K Ni.IMDA Ni.IMDA.L
Thioglycollic acid.	5.34±0.02	Glycine	4.85±0.03*
Thiolactic acid.	5.94±0.02	α-Alanine	4.59±0.02*
Thiomalic acid.	5.91±0.01	Aspartic acid.	5.18±0.04

*Values taken from literature—Reference No. 3.

ligand and secondary ligand. The values of $\log K_{NiL}^{Ni} - \log K_{NiL}^{Ni,IMDA}$ where L=aspartic acid is higher because aspartic acid has two negative charges and hence the repulsion between the primary charged ligand ion and secondary ligand ion is still more.

It is observed that in the (Ni. IMDA. thio-acid) systems, the behaviour of thioacids is similar to that of the σ -bonding amino acids. The $\log K_{NiL}^{Ni,IMDA} - \log K_{NiL}^{Ni,IMDA,L}$ values are nearly same for the pairs of glycine-Thioglycollic acid, α -alanine-thiolactic acid and aspartic acid-thiomalic acid. This indicates that in both the cases the factor responsible for the lowering of the values of $K_{NiL}^{Ni,IMDA}$ is electrostatic repulsion. The situation should have been different if there would have been significant Ni→S π interaction in the thio acid complexes. Therefore, the role of Ni→S π -interaction, if present, is not very significant. The strengthening of Ni→S bond in the mercapto acid complexes is due to σ -interactions as explained by Jorgenson and Klopman¹¹⁻¹².

References

1. I. P. MAVANI, C. R. JEJURKAR and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1972, 10, 742.
2. M. V. CHIDAMBARAM and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *Acta Chim. Hung.*, 1975, 75, 123.
3. J. D. JOSHI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1977, 15A, 57.
4. J. D. JOSHI and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, 50, 344.
5. B. E. LEACH and R. J. ANGELICI, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1969, 8, 907.
6. B. R. PANCHAL and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1972, 49, 469.
7. I. P. MAVANI, C. R. JEJURKAR and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, 49, 469.
8. S. N. DUBEY and R. C. MEHROTRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1966, 43, 73.
9. M. V. CHIDAMBARAM and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, 47, 881.
10. M. V. CHIDAMBARAM and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1970, 8, 941.
11. C. K. JORGENSEN, *Structure & Bonding*, 1967, 3, 106.
12. G. KLOPMAN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 90, 223.

Polarographic Reduction of Zn(II) and Mn(II) in the Presence of Aqueous Mixtures of Propylene Carbonate

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PROPYLENE carbonate which has a fairly high dielectric constant¹ ($\epsilon_{25^\circ} = 64.92$) is a new solvent in so far as the polarography of inorganic depolarizers in organic solvents is concerned². A survey of literature reveals that polarographic behaviour of inorganic depolarizers in aqueous mixtures of this solvent still remains untouched. With this aim in view a polarographic study of the behaviour of Zn(II) and Mn(II) in aqueous mixtures of propylene carbonate has been undertaken.

Experimental

ZnCl₂, MnCl₂, KCl were of B.D.H., A.R. grade. Propylene carbonate was a 'Riedel' product. All the solutions were prepared in conductivity water. The concentration of each depolarizer in the solutions was maintained at $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ and that of the supporting electrolyte (KCl) at 0.1 M. A manual polarograph (Toshniwal CLO2) in conjunction with polyflex galvanometer (Toshniwal PL50) was used. Triton X-100 (0.002%) was used to suppress the maximum of Mn(II). Since no maximum appeared in the case of Zn(II) in the present study, addition of suppressor was avoided. The temperature was kept at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. The d.m.e. had the following characteristics (in 0.1 M KCl, open circuit): $m = 2.34$ mg/sec, $t = 3.8$ sec, $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.2010$ mg^{2/3} sec^{-1/6}, $h_{0.01} = 58.50$ cm.

The number of electrons (n) involved in the electro-reduction of Zn(II) and Mn(II) being well established (n=2), Ilkovic equation was used to calculate the value of 'D' at different percentages of propylene carbonate in aqueous mixtures. The kinetic parameters of the electrode reaction of Zn(II) and Mn(II), wherever found irreversible, were calculated by Koutecky's treatment³⁻⁴.

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Results and Discussion

Figs. 1 and 2 depict the morphology of C-V curves of Zn(II) and Mn(II) in the presence of increasing percentages of propylene carbonate. The waves are well defined. However, the waves

Fig. 1. Polarograms of Zn(II) in the presence of different percentages (v/v) of propylene carbonate :

1. 0%, 2. 2%, 3. 4%, 4. 6%, 5. 10%, 6. 15%, 7. 20%.

Fig. 2. Polarograms of Mn(II) in the presence of different percentages (v/v) of propylene carbonate :

1. 0%, 2. 2%, 3. 4%, 4. 6%, 5. 10%, 6. 15%, 7. 20%.

could not be obtained at percentages greater than 20 as propylene carbonate was not miscible with water beyond this stage.

The plots of i_d vs. $h^{1/2}_{corr}$ and those of i_d vs. C are linear and pass through the origin thereby showing the diffusion-controlled nature of the electrode processes at different percentages of propylene carbonate.

It has been observed that i_d tends to decrease with increasing percentages of the organic solvent but the fact remains that this decrease is not much remarkable. As it is well known, the change occurring in i_d of a depolarizer is attributed to changes in diffusion coefficient, viscosity and ionic interaction the possibility of which increases with change in di-

electric constant. Interionic attraction may appreciably alter the ionic diffusion coefficient as compared to that in water. Since the dielectric constant of propylene carbonate ($\epsilon_{25^\circ} = 64.92$) is in close proximity to that of water ($\epsilon_{25^\circ} = 78.54$), the interionic attraction may not take place to an appreciable extent due to fairly high dielectric constant of propylene carbonate and consequently the diffusion coefficients of Zn(II) and Mn(II) are not altered appreciably.

$E_{1/2}$ values of both Zn(II) and Mn(II) get shifted to more negative potentials with increasing percentages of propylene carbonate. The total shift in $E_{1/2}$ of Mn(II) is 55 mV from the value in absence of organic solvent while in the case of Zn(II) it is 176 mV under the same experimental conditions. This significant negative shift in $E_{1/2}$ of Zn(II) vis-a-vis large increase in slope values (from 37 mV in the absence of propylene carbonate to 100 mV in the presence of 20% propylene carbonate) and ' $E_{3/4} - E_{1/4}$ ' values (from 37 mV in the absence of propylene carbonate to 95 mV in the presence of propylene carbonate) imply inhibition⁵ of the electrode reaction of Zn(II) as compared to that of Mn(II).

The slope value and ' $E_{3/4} - E_{1/4}$ ' values for Zn(II) and Mn(II) are of the order of 40 ± 2 mV which indicate that in aqueous medium the electrode reactions of Zn(II) and Mn(II) are quasi-reversible⁶⁻¹¹. However, with the addition of increasing amounts of propylene carbonate the slope values and ' $E_{3/4} - E_{1/4}$ ' values record a sharp increase in respect of the electrode reaction of Zn(II) as compared to that of Mn(II). On applying the criterion of total irreversibility¹² it has been found that ' α ' is less than 0.5 at different percentages of propylene carbonate in the case of Zn(II) thereby suggesting that the electrode reaction of Zn(II) becomes totally irreversible in the presence of aqueous mixtures of this solvent. In the case of Mn(II), on the other hand, ' α ' is not less than 0.5 signifying that the electrode reaction of Mn(II) does not change from quasireversibility to total irreversibility. Yet an increase in slope values and ' $E_{3/4} - E_{1/4}$ ' values does indicate that the electrode reaction of Mn(II) tends to irreversibility with increasing amounts of propylene carbonate.

The values of αn_a in the presence of 2, 4, 6, 10, 15 and 20 percent (v/v) propylene carbonate are respectively : 0.98, 0.81, 0.77, 0.59, 0.51 and 0.40 ; while those of $k_{r,h}^0$ (cm/sec) are : 1.60×10^{-8} , 3.45×10^{-9} , 2.13×10^{-9} , 4.38×10^{-10} , 3.16×10^{-10} and 7.35×10^{-11} . A perusal of αn_a values reveals that the product ' αn_a ' records a decrease with increasing percentages of propylene carbonate. The polarographic reduction of Zn(II) is a well-established two-electron process and therefore, the number of electrons involved in the rate determining step can either be 1 or 2. Since the decrease in ' αn_a ' values is indiscrete and at no stage the two consecutive values vary by a factor of 2, the possibility of decrease in

the value of the product ' αn_a ' due to a change in ' n_a ' may be ruled out. Thus, it can be safely concluded that it is ' α ' which is decreasing. ' α ', the transfer coefficient signifies¹³ the fraction of the applied voltage which favours the cathodic reaction, $Zn^{2+} + 2e \rightarrow Zn$. A decrease in the value of ' α ' thus implies that the transfer of electron/electrons is made increasingly difficult. In other words the electrode reaction of Zn(II) is rendered increasingly irreversible with increasing percentages of propylene carbonate. The shift in $E_{1/2}$ to more negative potentials and increase in slope values of log plots are also in agreement with the above conclusion.

A decrease in the value of $k_{f,h}^0$ with increasing percentages of propylene carbonate lends support to the conclusion arrived at on the basis of ' αn_a ' values.

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References

1. R. PAYNE and I. E. THEODORON, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1972, 76, 2892.
2. R. TAKAHASHI, *Talanta*, 1965, 12, 1211.
3. J. KOUTECKY, *Chem. Listy*, 1953, 47, 323; *Colln. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1953, 18, 597.
4. J. KOUTECKY and J. CEZEK, *Coll. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1956, 21, 836.
5. J. HEYROSKY and J. KUTA, "Principles of Polarography", Academic Press, New York, 1966, p, 299.
6. J. N. GAUR, D. S. JAIN and A. KUMAR, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, 13, 165.
7. P. S. VERMA, D. S. JAIN and J. N. GAUR, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, 13, 586.
8. P. DELAHAY, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 1430.
9. H. MATSUDA and Y. AYABE, *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1959, 63, 1164.
10. J. KORYTA, *Electrochim Acta*, 1962, 6, 67.
11. P. J. GELLINGS *Z. Elektrochem., Ber., Busenges, Phys. Chem.*, 1962, 66, 477, 481, 799; 1963, 67, 167.
12. R. GOTO and I. TACHI, *Proc. Intern. Polarogr. Congr.*, 1951, Vol. I, p. 69.
13. P. DELAHAY, 'New Instrumental Methods in Electrochemistry', Interscience Publ., New York, 1954, p, 33.

Standard Heat of Formation of Thorium Tetraacetate†

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WE report in this work the heats of solution of crystalline thorium tetraacetate, $ThAc_4(c)$, and pure acetic acid, $HAc(Ac=CH_3COO)$ in

1M- and 6M-HCl solutions respectively at 298K. The standard heat of formation of $ThAc_4(c)$ can be evaluated by considering the following thermochemical reactions:

As the ionization constant of acetic acid is of the order of 10^{-5} , it would dissolve in HCl solution without ionization as shown in Eq.(2).

From the above equations, we find

$$\Delta H_f^\circ ThAc_4(c) = -(\Delta H_1 - 4\Delta H_2) + \Delta H_f^\circ Th^{4+}(\text{in } x \text{ M-HCl}) + 4\Delta H_f^\circ HAc(l) \quad (4)$$

and

$$\Delta H_f^\circ ThAc_4(c) = -(\Delta H_1 - 4\Delta H_2 - \Delta H_3) + \Delta H_f^\circ ThCl_4(c) + \Delta H_f^\circ HAc(l) - 4\Delta H_f^\circ HCl(\text{in } x \text{ M-HCl}) \quad (5)$$

Experimental

Thorium tetraacetate was prepared by refluxing a mixture of BDH 'AnalaR' crystalline thorium nitrate pentahydrate, $Th(NO_3)_4 \cdot 5H_2O(c)$, with a 2 : 1 mixture of glacial acetic acid and acetic anhydride for several hours¹. A white crystalline solid separated which was washed several times with glacial acetic acid in a fritted-glass filter stick. The final product was vacuum dried at 60° for several hours until there was no loss in weight of the sample. It was analysed for thorium (Found : Th, 49.3; Calc. for $ThAc_4(c)$: Th, 49.6%). 'AnalaR' glacial acetic acid was triply distilled under reduced pressure before use.

TABLE 1—HEATS OF SOLUTION OF THORIUM TETRAACETATE AND ACETIC ACID IN 175 ML AQUEOUS HYDROCHLORIC ACID AT 298K IN KJ MOL⁻¹.

Solvents	Compounds	Weight (gms.)	Concn. (mole/l)	ΔH (kJ mol ⁻¹)	Mean
1M-HCl	$ThAc_4(c)$	0.25076	0.00306	-45.0	-46.1 ± 0.2
		0.35125	0.00429	-46.5	
		0.38148	0.00466	-46.0	
6M-HCl	$ThAc_4(c)$	0.14216	0.00173	-36.0	-35.7 ± 0.5
		0.17867	0.00218	-35.8	
		0.19078	0.00232	-35.2	
1M-HCl	HAc(l)	1.5500	0.148	-0.80	-0.80
		1.6671	0.159	-0.80	
		1.8631	0.177	-0.80	
6M-HCl	HAc(l)	1.6903	0.161	-0.5	-0.5
		1.9236	0.183	-0.5	
		2.3759	0.226	-0.6	

A closed-system calorimeter described earlier was

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